

Industrial Revolution and Its Effects on Communication

S. R. Sreeja

Ph.D. Research Scholar, Department of History
Nirmala College for Women For women, Cbe-18

Dr. Priya Premlatha,

Assistant professor
Department of History, Nirmala college for women, cbe-18

A B S T R A C T

The Industrial Revolution began in England about 1750-1760. It is one of the most distinguished turning points in human history. The introduction of new inventions by the scientists such as steam engines, telegraph, telephone, etc. made man's work easier. The ability to communicate across long distances improved dramatically during the Industrial Revolution. It began with the invention of the electric telegraph by Samuel Morse in 1844. This system allows it to be transmitted much quicker and cheaper than old methods of conveying messages through pigeons, drums, smoke, fire, gestures, sounds, pictures, words, etc. The interaction between people based on communication becomes an essential role in the progress of civilization the present paper discuss the early means of communication and the modern telegram and its benefits to the people and the government.

Key words: Industrial Revolution, Communication, Electric Telegraph, Samuel Morse, People and the government.

Introduction

In modern times particularly during the 19th and 20th centuries, Britain and Europe witnessed the kind of Transformation, this transformation made man's work even easier. The great principles of science and technology are evolved from the scientists to make life even better. Scientists began to apply those principles in practical fields, especially in the fields of industries and communication.¹ Thus the common man was able to enjoy the benefits even though he may not have any idea or much knowledge of scientific knowledge. Today, the communication revolution has become compulsory among the people of the modern world. Thus Industrial Revolution made a remarkable change in the lives of Man so that he could build a new society and civilization.

Methodology

The present paper is an attempt to trace the effects of industrial revolution on communication and how telegram emerged as a new means to communicate across the globe. The study is completely narrative and descriptive in nature

Industrial Revolution

The word revolution is used to describe economic changes that occurred in England in the middle of the 18th century². though few historians place or argued that the beginning of revolution started in the mid of 16th century but most historians hold a view that it taken off about the 1780s. Before the 18th century, England was an agricultural and rural economy. Much of the rural population were engaged in domestic manufacturing of textiles or indulged in agriculture mining or building needs. People and their life were not developed it was a pre-industrial era but after 1780 industrial revolution has come into existence because of its existence many industries and manufacturing units emerged all over the towns of English society and the development of industries attracted people of rural areas to migrate into cities that made an increase of manufacturing units and improvement of technology has come into force.³ The industrial revolution also brought a new revolution in transportation and communication it speed up their contacts all over the world and made merchants come closer to other parts of the country the invention of the telegram, and the telephone made tremendous changes to shift their business to the next level⁴

Communication

Communication is the exchange of emotions between individuals through human-known common symbols. In 1928 the English literary critic and author I.A. Richards offered one of the first and best definitions of communication.

*Communication takes place when one mind so acts upon its environment that another mind is influenced, and in that other mind an experience occurs which is like the experience in the first mind, and is caused in part by that experience.*⁵

Importance of Communication

- Communication helps people to share their thoughts and feelings and also to build a good relationship, solve problems and make decisions.
- Communication plays a major role in every aspect of human life. Without communication, it would be difficult for humans to interact with one another and their progress of life will be less functioned. Communication is all about listening and understanding.
- It helps to understand better and issues can be solved when both people are engaged in communication.
- No matter what type of communication we are using, It should ensure that it should effectively reaches the receiver without any misunderstandings, it is very important to have good eye contact and body language so that the communication will be better⁶

Types of Communication

There are two main types of communication used daily: verbal and nonverbal communication. Verbal communication is also known as spoken communication. It includes face-to-face interaction. Television, radio, and other media and Nonverbal communication generally involve body language and gestures. Non-verbal does not use words to communicate. The advancement of technology has modified the methods of communication. Every year new devices were introduced. The Internet has made the evolution of communication more effective. It could send messages with one click. Computers, mobile phones, laptops, radios, etc., all help us to communicate faster and cheaper. Before the Industrial Revolution and even sometime after

that, People had to wait for days, weeks, and months to hear from others. But the introduction of the telegram was made an advancement of revolution in communication it is the forerunner of present-day technologies communication. And now technology has made it easier. The latest applications, devices enable us to have secure communication with others.⁷

Early Means of Communication

Early means of communication took place through the ages by employing gestures, sounds, pictures, and words. In those days they played a major role in passing their ideas, feelings, and images from one person, people, or generation to another. New technological devices are a boon to mankind it was more convenient, accessible, and speed. The people of the world have been drawn to almost instant contact, for good or ill, in peace or in war.

Usual Means of Communication In The Early Period

- Carrier pigeons serve as a messenger since the early days tiny rolls of paper were placed inside the capsules attached to their back or tied up in their legs
- Writings, pictured carved on the rocks depict the messages which could be seen especially in Nebraska and in southwest regions
- Native Africans used drums to relay their messages to distant parts.
- A notched message sticks of early days.
- The ship bell was an important means of communication
- Braille enabled the blind to read
- The messages transmitted by teletype are automatically recorded by a teletypewriter at the other end.⁸ Primitive tribes sent messages from hill to hill with the help of fire.
- France used semaphores to communicate and it was stationed at the top of the hills in sight of each other; the messages were sent simply by moving the arms on semaphores. It was used during the period of Napoleon

Prehistoric man learned to beat on resonant logs and tree trunks with a stick then to make more effective drums of stretched membranes were used and finally to use the knowledge he extend the range of his voice, rhythms, and intonations applied to drum beats which could be made to express emotions and ideas. People also communicated through the drums, the reed pipe, the bone whistle, or the ram's horn to pre-arrange a set of meanings for certain sounds and sequences. Later counting beats led to the development of codes. Even Smoke signals and fire also played a major role in communication During the Ancient period, particularly in China, Egypt, Assyria, and Greece used smoke signals and fires using communication .Smoke signaled by day and fires by night. Signal fires were also recorded as having been used by the Picts against the Roman invaders of Britain in the 1st century AD and by American Indians in Ohio in early colonial times⁹.

Overseas Mail System Before 1815

From the 17th century, merchant letters had arrived at British ports by private ships, while official correspondence was often carried by naval vessels. The arriving private ship letters were sent from the port of arrival to London where they were marked up with three charges; the ship letter charge, the fee paid to the ship's master for each letter handed over and the inland postage according to the number of miles the letter had been conveyed by road from the port of entry via London to the place of address. The addressee could not receive this letter before having paid the total amount due. From the 1760's the post office issued individually named ship letter hand stamps to post masters at ports in all parts of Britain.¹⁰

Modern Telegram

The word telegraph was first coined in France around 1792 to describe a pioneer optical-relay semaphore system invented by a French physician and an inventor Claude Chappe. The literal derivation from the Greek tele, 'far' Grapher" to write".¹¹

Birth of Telegram

In 1832 the American painter, Samuel F.B Morse, on his return voyage in the packet ship named "Sully", listened to a fellow traveler Charles Jackson, an electric doctor and inventor, who discussed the phenomenon and application of electromagnetism. He also demonstrated that an electric impulse could be carried along a very long wire this sparked an idea in his mind .By 1837 with the help of the famous physicist Joseph Henry and his friend Leonard Gale, his

shipboard sketch came into existence. He constructed a forty-mile line from Washington D.C to Baltimore, on May 24, 1844, the first message sent by Morse over the line and he trapped out a famous word” What hath God wrought” this made the birth of telegraph communication. in the year 1832¹²

During the 18th century, Great Britain established the first modern postal service in 1840. For carrying letters anywhere in the country government set a rate of a penny, and later on all other countries copied the British Postal system. That was the first spark in the technological invention to introduce the new and fastest means of communication called telegram. The telegraph was the first invention that greatly increased the speed of man’s communication. Until the invention of the telegraph, messages were the chief means by which men could communicate with each other at a distance. Messages sent by telegraph travelled with the speed of electricity through wires or about 10,000 miles per second. Important news reports and business messages could be sent across mountains and deserts and even under the bed of the oceans. Since 1870 the government has owned the Telegraph lines, which provided cheap but not very convenient service to the public British cable companies control most of the world's cable and can communicate almost instantly with most parts of the world. There is no separate office organized to operate the telegram service but it was smoothly operated under the postal department¹³

It takes not more than half an hour at one time shall be devoted to the transmission of any telegrams. If there is any urgent telegram to be sent within the commonwealth shall be accepted by the public and charged double the payment than the ordinary fee¹⁴

Beneficial to the People And Government

- The telegraph played a major role in the civil war. It was first employed in the military of the Allied army in Bulgaria where lines were erected to connect headquarters with troops units in 1855 in the same war submarine cables were laid down across the Black Sea.
- In the American Civil War telegraph was the only source of communication far away, to operate this telegraph they appointed the operators in large numbers.
- In Spanish-American wars, landlines and cable telegraphs were geared for the first time to meet the needs of newspapers.

- In the Russo-Japanese War, radio telegraphy was used for the first time(1904-1905)
- World War 1 brought the first use of Teleprinter encryption ¹⁵
- The government of England at once extended the telegraph to all sections of the society and reduced the rate to one cent a word
- In England, the Government telegraphs were of great benefit to the people. Rates were low, and all newspapers there stood on equal terms regarding telegraph tolls.¹⁶
- The cheapest and prompt services of the telegraph became an essential social as well as a business utility.

Effects of Telegram and How It Revolutionized the Communication

- The telegraph changed American society by giving them a great advancement to communicate long distances it serves at an unprecedented speed and volume.
- The electric telegraph helped the military to communicate tactically in the war zones and let journalists and newspapers send and receive news fast and efficiently
- Telegraph was also used in railways to know the departure and arrivals of trains.¹⁷
- The telegraph represented a revolution in communications rivaling both the printing press and the Internet. Indeed, thanks to Morse's invention, communication was, for the first time in history, no longer limited to the speed at which a physical message could pass between locations. The telegraph could be operated through signal lines thus it is much faster and more reliable and it could transmit messages over long distances when compared to messengers and smoke signals¹⁸
- The telegraph affected the distribution of power for a European big banking family. Before the introduction of the telegraph, the big banking family Rothschild developed a communication system based on couriers and carrier pigeons their couriers connected the main European economic centers. This gave them a competitive advantage for profit earning which disappeared with the introduction of the telegraph. James de Rothschild once said that 'it was a crying shame that the telegraph has been established'.

- Telegraph also made an impact on the emancipation of women as they were often employed as telegraph operators.
- In society, they also get an opportunity to explore things they could shine through with secure jobs, greater rights, and possibilities of education. Women in industrialized countries started getting more important positions¹⁹

Conclusion

The telegraph accelerated the speed of business transactions during the late nineteenth century and contributed to industrialization it was one of the most important inventions of this century. It revolutionized communication making it possible to connect and communicate with people from far away. Thus the telegraph played a decisive role in the lives of people all over the world.

Reference

¹ B.V Rao, *World History*, Sterling Publishers Pvt Ltd, New Delhi, 1985, p.263

² B.K.Gokhale” *History of Modern World*” Himalaya Publishing House, Bombay, 1900-1960, p.519

³ Bolivia Cervantes “*The New Encyclopedia Britannica –Macropaedia Volume-18 Knowledge in Depth*” William Benton Publisher 1943-1973, Helen Hemingway Benton-1973-1974, p.260

⁴ “*The World Book Encyclopedia*” Volume-16” T” The Quarrie Corporation, USA 1948, p.8108

⁵ Gordon, George. N.. "Communication". *Encyclopedia Britannica*, <https://www.britannica.com>, 3 Jul. 2023

⁶ www.Inter observers. in “, *What is Communication? , Explanation, Importance, Types and Skills*, April 24, 2022

⁷ Kalam time *Evolution of Communication from Ancient to Modern Times*” January 22, 2021

⁸ “*The World Book Encyclopedia*” Volume-16” T” The Quarrie Corporation, USA 1948, p.1628,1642&1643

⁹Bolivia Cervantes “*The New Encyclopedia Britannica –Macropaedia* Volume-18 knowledge in depth”, 1768-15th edition, p.473

¹⁰ Jean-Michel Johnston “*Networks of Modernity, Germany in the Age of the telegraph, 1830-1880*” Oxford University Press Oxford, United Kingdom-2021, P-2

¹¹ “*The World Book Encyclopedia*” Volume-16, the Quarrie Corporation, USA 1948, p.7934

¹² R. Parthasarathy “*Paths of Innovators in Science, Engineering, and Technology, Volume 2*”, University Press, IIT Chennai, p.9

¹³ “*The World Book Encyclopedia*” Volume-7” G” The Quarrie Corporation, USA 1948, p.3138

¹⁴ “*Commonwealth of Australia Gazette*”, PART-1, Australian Government Public Service, 1902, p.261

¹⁵ *The New Encyclopedia Britannica –Macropaedia* Volume-18 Knowledge In Depth, Bolivia Cervantes Founded 1768-15th Edition, P.76